

Physico-chemical characterization of activated carbons from local lignocellulosic biomass (Niger)

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Abstract

This study presents the physico-chemical characterization of activated carbons produced from local lignocellulosic biomass, notably the core shells of *Balanites aegyptiaca* (L.) Del. (Adoua), and *Hyphaene thebaica* (L.) Mart. (Gorouba) by chemical activation with orthophosphoric acid (H₃PO₄). Elaborated Activated Carbons (EACs) were characterized using experimental techniques such as: X-ray Diffraction using a Shimadzu XRD-6000 diffractometer, Infra-Red (IR-TF) using a spectrometer (Bruker Vector-22 Fourier transform spectrometer; ATR-FTIR), SEM using a Hitachi device at 20 kV and Raman spectroscopy. The results of this study show that Elaborated Activated Carbons did not detect any detectable crystallized species on the surface; the existence of several types of pore types (micropores, mesopores and macropores) of pores. Elaborated activated carbons have developed functional groups (carboxylic hydroxyls (O-H), asymmetrical and symmetrical C-H, C=C alkene, C=O carbonyl, C-O and C-C alkene, aliphatic and aromatic); cumulative pore volumes (BJH) vary from 0.269688 to 0.560185 cm³ g⁻¹; CAEs are capable of adsorbing molecules of micropore, mesopore and macropore sizes.

Keywords: Biomass; *Balanites aegyptiaca*; *Hyphaene thebaica*; Activated carbon; Characterization

1. Introduction

As one of the extraction methods of choice, adsorption is the most widely used technique due to its efficiency, ease of implementation and affordable investment cost [1,2, 3]. However, this method requires the choice of an adsorbent with good characteristics (high adsorption capacity, availability, low cost, etc.) [4,5]. Microporous adsorbents are widely used for the extraction of chemical species from aqueous or gaseous phases, thanks to their excellent adsorption capacity [2,5-6]. This capacity is linked to the high specific surface area and porosity development of these adsorbents [7-9]. The use of activated carbon (AC) as an adsorbent is of interest in the treatment of industrial wastewater [10,11]. Activated carbon is essentially a carbonaceous material with a porous structure. This structure is generally obtained after high-temperature carbonization of lignocellulosic biomass. Various types of AC exist, with specific surface areas ranging from 100 to 2,500 m² g⁻¹ [12,13]. Despite the availability of biomass in the sub-region, African countries continue to import activated carbons (ACs) in large quantities for a variety of applications, including industrial wastewater treatment and ore processing. This is why it seems necessary to develop and characterize ACs from local lignocellulosic biomasses, in

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particular the core shells of *Balanites aegyptiaca* (L.) Del. (Adoua), and *Hyphaene thebaica* (L.) Mart. (Gorouba) by chemical activation. The selected biomasses come from wild trees that are widespread in Niger and produce seasonal fruits consumed by the population. The pits of these fruits end up in the municipal landfill as urban waste. They constitute abundant agri-food waste that is more or less difficult to biodegrade in tropical countries. The use of these cores in this work has a dual advantage: on the one hand, to produce activated carbons, and on the other, to add value to the waste. Elaborated activated carbons (CAEs) were characterized using experimental techniques such as XRD, IR, SEM and Raman spectroscopy.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

XRD is a surface analysis technique used to determine the nature of crystalline species present on the surface of materials. For activated carbon samples, analysis was carried out using a Shimadzu XRD-6000 diffractometer equipped with a copper anode $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm; 40 kV and 30 Ma kV. These analyses were carried out at the State Key Laboratory of Chemical Engineering, Beijing University of Chemical Technology, People's Republic of China.

2.2. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR)

FT-IR is based on the absorption of infrared radiation by the material being analyzed. By detecting the characteristic vibrations of chemical bonds, it enables qualitative analysis of the chemical functions present in CA. The spectrum of CA was recorded at room temperature in total reflection mode using a spectrometer (Bruker Vector-22 Fourier transform spectrometer; ATR-FTIR) in the wave number range 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} . These analyses were carried out at the State Key Laboratory of Chemical Resource Engineering of Beijing University of Chemical Technology in the People's Republic of China.

2.3. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM is used to describe the morphology of Elaborated Activated Carbon. In these studies, observations were made using a 20 kV Hitachi instrument. These analyses were carried out at the State Key Laboratory of Chemical Resource Engineering of Beijing University of Chemical Technology in the People's Republic of China.

2.4. Raman microscopy

This technique complements XRD. It is a method for observing and characterizing the molecular composition and external structure of a material. In these studies, Raman spectra were recorded at room temperature with a Microscopic Confocal spectrometer (Jobin Yvon Horiba HR800), using an Ar⁺ laser as the excitation source at a wavelength of 532 nm. These analyses were carried out at the State Key Laboratory of Chemical Resource Engineering of Beijing University of Chemical Technology in the People's Republic of China.

2.5. Determining the porosity of CAEs

The surface and volume distributions of CAEs are determined by the Density Functional Theory (DFT) and BJH methods [13].

3. Results

3.1. X-ray diffraction analysis

Figure 1 shows diffractograms of activated carbons made from *Balanites aegyptiaca* (L.) Del activated with 30 % and 40 % ortho-phosphoric acid.

Figure 1 Diffractograms of CAEs

3.2. Analysis by infrared spectroscopy

The infrared (IR) spectra of activated carbons made from *Balanites aegyptiaca* (L.) Del activated with 30 % and 40 % ortho-phosphoric acid are shown in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2 Infrared spectrum of CA-30 %

Figure 3 Infrared spectrum of CA-40 %

Analysis of the infrared spectrum of activated carbons has enabled us to identify the main signals [15-17] (Table 1).

Table 1 CAE functional groupings

Type	Wave number (cm ⁻¹)		Vibration frequency assignment
	CA-30 %	CA-40 %	
Peaks	3438	3444	Carboxylated hydroxyls (O-H)
Signals	2923-2853	2918	Assymetrical and symmetrical C-H
Bands	2800 and 1735	2862 and 1731	C=C groups
Signals	1701	1702	C=O groups
Potato	1493 and 1321	-	C-O groups
Peak	1164.05	1189.46	C-C (alkene, aliphatic and aromatic)

3.3. Scanning electron microscopy analysis

In order to visualize the external morphology of CAEs, scanning electron microscopy was performed on 40 % *Balanites aegyptiaca* CA in order to see the effect of activation. Figure 4 shows the CAE images.

Figure 4 SEM images of CAEs

3.4. DFT pore volume distributions

Figure 5 shows the isotherms of the CAE volume distributions and the CAC.

Figure 5 Volume distributions of CAEs and CA-C

Figures 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 show the derivatives of the volume distributions of the CAEs and the CAC.

Figure 6 CA-BA-H₃PO₄-25 % volume derivative

Figure 7 Volume derivative of CA-BA-H₃PO₄-40%

Figure 8 Volume derivative of CA-C

Figure 9 CA-HT-H₃PO₄-25% volume derivative

Figure 10 CA-HT-H₃PO₄-40 % volume derivative

The results of the volume distributions using the DFT method are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Distribution of pore volumes using the DFT method

Ref. Samples	Pore volume (cm ³ g ⁻¹) < 14.83 Å	Total pore volume (cm ³ g ⁻¹) ≤ 1366.77 Å
CA-BA-H ₃ PO ₄ -25%	0.46474	0.56392
CA-BA-H ₃ PO ₄ -40%	0.32408	0.74954
CA-C	0.27685	0.38510
CA-HT-H ₃ PO ₄ -25%	0.19820	0.25251
CA-HT-H ₃ PO ₄ -40%	0.33989	0.41774

3.4.1. Cumulative pore volumes BJH

The cumulative pore volumes according to the BJH method are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Cumulative pore volumes using the BJH method

Ref. Samples	Cumulative pore volume (cm ³ g ⁻¹ STP)	
	Adsorption	Desorption
CA-BA-H ₃ PO ₄ -25%	0.531322	0.046312
CA-BA-H ₃ PO ₄ -40%	0.560185	0.264042
CA-C	0.269688	0.172604
CA-HT-H ₃ PO ₄ -25%	0.278645	0.016532
CA-HT-H ₃ PO ₄ -40%	0.400906	0.041661

3.4.2. Average pore diameters of CAEs and CAC.

The average pore sizes are determined using the BET and BJH methods (adsorption and desorption). The results for the average pore diameters are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Average pore diameter (Å) using the BET and BJH methods

Ref. Samples	BET Method	BJH Method	
	Adsorption	Adsorption	Desorption
CA-BA-H ₃ PO ₄ -25%	17.3617	21.331	42.400
CA-BA-H ₃ PO ₄ -40%	22.5136	27.023	41.993
CA-C	22.3516	37.995	69.847
CA-HT-H ₃ PO ₄ -25%	16.9788	20.525	52.964
CA-HT-H ₃ PO ₄ -40%	17.6995	21.537	46.316

3.4.3. DFT pore size distributions

Surface and volume pore distributions are determined by the DFT (Density Functional Theory) model.

3.5. Surface pore distributions

Figure 11 shows the isotherms of the surface distributions of CAEs and CA-C.

Figure 11 Surface distributions of CAEs and CAC

Figures 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16 show the derivatives of the surface distributions of the CAEs and the CA-C.

Figure 12 Surface derivative of CA-BA-H₃PO₄-25 %

Figure 13 Surface derivative of CA-BA-H₃PO₄-40 %

Figure 14 Surface derivative of CA-C

Figure 15 Surface derivative of CA-HT-H₃PO₄- 25%

Figure 16 Surface derivative of CA-HT-H₃PO₄-40%

The results of the surface distributions are presented in Table 5.

Table 5 Distribution of pore areas using the DFT method

Ref. Samples	Pore area (m ² g ⁻¹) > 1366.77 Å	Total pore surface area (m ² g ⁻¹) ≥ 14.83 Å
CA-BA-H ₃ PO ₄ -25%	0.000	97.772
CA-BA-H ₃ PO ₄ -40%	8.063	332.591
CA-C	24.392	84.242
CA-HT-H ₃ PO ₄ -25%	0.000	58.795
CA-HT-H ₃ PO ₄ -40%	1.960	76.423

4. Discussion

Analysis of Figure 1 shows that the two diffractograms did not detect any crystallized species on the surface of the activated carbons produced. These would be characteristic of an amorphous material that does not have any detectable crystallized species on its surface [18].

Analysis of Figures 2 and 3 shows that ACEs from local biomasses have functional groups. Table 1 shows:

- Peaks attributable to carboxylic hydroxyl (O-H) groups at 3438 and 3444 cm⁻¹ for CA-30 % and CA-30 % respectively;
- Signals attributable to asymmetric and symmetric C-H (2923-2853 and 2918 cm⁻¹ for CA-30% and CA-30% respectively);
- Bands attributable to C=C groups (2800 and 1735, 2862 and 1731);
- Signals attributable to C=O groups (1701 and 1702 cm⁻¹);
- Peaks at 1493 and 1321 cm⁻¹ attributable to C-O groups;
- Peaks at 1164.05 and 1189.46 cm⁻¹ attributable to C-C (alkene, aliphatic, and aromatic).

The images in Figure 4 show that the biomass activation reaction created pores of different sizes (micropores, mesopores, and macropores). The existence of several types of pores after chemical activation with phosphoric acid has been observed in the literature [19].

Analysis of the results presented in Table 3 shows that:

- Adsorption: the calculated cumulative pore volumes (BJH) range from 0.269688 to 0.560185 cm³ g⁻¹ for CA-C and CA-BA-H₃PO₄-40% respectively. They are then ranked as follows for CA-HT-H₃PO₄-25% (0.278645 cm³ g⁻¹) < CA-HT-H₃PO₄-40% (0.400906 cm³ g⁻¹) < CA-BA-H₃PO₄-25% (0.531322 cm³ g⁻¹). The V_{poreux,cul} increases as a function of the percentage of the activating agent for BA and HT. Thus, the best v_{poreux,cul} would be obtained at 40%. The v_{poreux,cul} of all caes exceeds that of CA-C. All V_{poreux,cul} values are between 0.2 and 0.6 cm³ g⁻¹. This confirms the microporosity phenomenon observed on the samples;
- For desorption, these V_{poreux,cul} values range from 0.016532 to 0.264042 cm³ g⁻¹ for CA-HT-H₃PO₄-25% and CA-BA-H₃PO₄-40%, respectively. They then follow in the following order for CA-HT-H₃PO₄-40% (0.041661 cm³ g⁻¹) < CA-BA-H₃PO₄-25% (0.046312 cm³ g⁻¹) < CA-C (0.172604 cm³ g⁻¹). Apart from CA-BA-H₃PO₄-40%, all samples have values between 0.02 and 0.1 cm³ g⁻¹, confirming the mesoporous nature of these samples. In the case of CA-BA-H₃PO₄-40%, this could be due to the external surface area developed by the latter, as it is proportional to V_{poreux}.

Analysis of the results presented in Table 4 shows that the average pore diameter values determined by the BET method range from 16.9788 to 22.5136 Å for CA-HT-H₃PO₄-25% and CA-BA-H₃PO₄-40%, respectively. This is consistent with S_{BET}, S_L, and V_{poreux}. They then follow in the following order for CA-BA-H₃PO₄-25% (17.3617 Å) < CA-HT-H₃PO₄-40% (17.6995 Å) < CA-C (22.3516 Å). These show that the d_{moy} of CA-BA-H₃PO₄-25%, CA-HT-H₃PO₄-25%, and CA-HT-H₃PO₄-40% are less than 20 Å (2 nm). Thus, they correspond to the micropore size distribution. In addition, these values exceed 7 Å. This indicates that they are supermicropores. In the case of CA-C and CA-BA-H₃PO₄-40%, the d_{moy} values are between 20 and 500 Å. They are attributable to the mesopore size distribution. These further confirm the attribution of adsorption types. These samples are capable of adsorbing molecules of micropore and mesopore sizes. Research groups have noted that increasing the orthophosphoric acid impregnation ratio leads to a decrease in microporosity. The calculated access pore diameters, based on the desorption branch (BJH), range from 41.400 to 69.847 Å for CA-BA-H₃PO₄-40% and CA-C, respectively. For the other samples, they range from CA-BA-H₃PO₄-25% (42.400 Å) < CA-HT-H₃PO₄-40% (46.316 Å) < CA-HT-H₃PO₄-25% (52.964 Å). The diameters of the access pores obtained are essentially uniform, i.e., mesopores (20 < d_{mean} < 500 Å). The actual pore diameters calculated from the adsorption branch range from 20.525 to 37.995 Å for CA-HT-H₃PO₄-25% and CA-C, respectively. They are followed internally by CA-BA-H₃PO₄-25% (21.331 Å) < CA-HT-H₃PO₄-40% (21.537 Å) < CA-BA-H₃PO₄-40% (27.023 Å). All these values are between 20 and 500 Å. This confirms the mesoporous nature of the access pore diameters [13-20-22].

5. Conclusion

The objectives of this work are the physical and chemical characterization of activated carbons. These studies show that:

- XRD diffractograms did not detect any crystallized species on the surface of the activated carbons;
- There are several types of pores (micropores, mesopores, and macropores). (SEM images);
- ACEs made from local biomass have developed functional groups such as carboxylic hydroxyl (O-H) groups, asymmetric and symmetric C-H groups, C=C, C=O, C-O, and C-C (alkene, aliphatic, and aromatic) groups;
- The calculated cumulative pore volumes (BJH) range from 0.269688 to 0.560185 cm³ g⁻¹ for CA-C and CA-BA-H₃PO₄-40% respectively;
- The V_{poreux,cul} increases in proportion to the percentage of activating agent for BA and HT ;
- The V_{poreux,cul} of all CAEs exceeds that of CA-C ;
- All V_{poreux,cul} values are between 0.2 and 0.6 cm³ g⁻¹ ;
- This confirms the microporosity phenomenon observed in the samples;
- All samples have values between 0.02 and 0.1 cm³ g⁻¹, confirming the mesoporous nature of these samples;
- CAEs are capable of adsorbing molecules of micropore and mesopore sizes.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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